



Additional Figure 1. qPCR validation of select gametocyte genes



Additional Figure 2. Transcript abundance of ApiAP2 transcription factors during *P. falciparum* gametocyte development



Additional Figure 3. Transcript abundance of *ap2-g* (line) and downstream genes (ribbon, identified in Josling et al. 2019)